

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE USE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF KOKAND SCIENTISTS ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV

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Annotasiya: maqolada sharqshunos-tarixchi olim Asomiddin O'rinboevning Qo'qon xonligi tarixiga oid ilmiy tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati xaqida so'z boradi. Bugunki kungacha bu merosdan O'zbekiston, Tojikiston, Qirg'iziston, Qozog'iston va boshqa davlatlardagi Qo'qon xonligi tarixi bo'yicha tadqiqot olib borgan olimlar unumli foydalanib kelayotgani tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qo'qon, qo'lyozma, iqtisod, soliq, geografik.

Аннотация: В статье говорится о значении научных изысканий ученого-востоковеда-историка Асомиддина Оринбоева по истории Коканского ханства. Проанализировано, что ученые, проводившие исследования по истории Кокандского ханства в Узбекистане, Таджикистане, Киргизии, Казахстане и других странах, и по сей день успешно используют это наследие.

Ключевые слова: Коканд, рукопись, хозяйство, налог, географический.

Annotation: The article talks about the significance of the scientific researches of the orientalist-historian scholar Asomiddin Orinboev on the history of the Kokan Khanate. It has been analyzed that scientists who have conducted research on the history of the Kokand Khanate in Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan and other countries are making good use of this heritage to this day.

Key words: Kokand, manuscript, economy, tax, geographical.

INTRODUCTION

Asomiddin Orinboev, being an Oriental scholar, conducted scientific research based on manuscript sources written by local historians in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate. In particular, the works “Tarihi jadayi Tashkand” written by Muhammad Salihkhoja and «Khulasat-ul Ahval» belonging to Abu Ubaidullah Muhammad Tashkandi are among them.

Academician D. Yusupova said that in 1964, 1971, 1987, collections of Oriental manuscripts were prepared by Asomiddin Orinboev and L.M. Epifanova. Asomiddin Orinboev personally participated in the creation of volumes VII, IX, XI of the collection of Oriental manuscripts and edited them. He created the descriptions of the sources in the catalogs after reviewing the manuscript sources on the history of the Kokan Khanate included in these volumes one by one. This is discussed in the following paragraphs.

Another important study by A. Orinboev in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate was published as an article under the name «Neizvestnaya rukopis po istorii Kokandskogo khanstva». [1.1.33-38 p.] It is in this article that an important manuscript source related to the history of the khanate is analyzed. This manuscript, researched by A. Orinboev, is important for the in-depth study of the history of the economic life of the Kokan Khanate, especially the tax system.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS: (MAIN PART) .

It is appropriate to divide Asomuddin Orinboev's research on the history of the Kokan Khanate into three groups. One group includes works published during the Soviet era . The second group consists of studies published during the period of independence, and the third group consists of articles and works of foreign researchers that reflect some issues of the history of the Kokhan Khanate.

V. Ploskikh [2.1.262 p.] Sh. Vahidov [3.1.154 p.] and others are among the authors of the work included in the first group.

In the section of V. Ploskikh's scientific research entitled «Tax system of the Kokan Khanate and other forms of exploitation» based on the scientific article of Asomuddin Orinboev, one of the manuscript sources that illuminates the history of the Khanate «Khulosa ul-akhval» describes the negative situations that occurred in the process of collecting taxes from Kyrgyz and Kazakh nomadic herders and the state The response of officials is highlighted. [2.2.368 p.] The second group of literature includes studies published and carried out after Uzbekistan gained independence, Sh.Vahidov[4.1.], Z.Ilhomov[5.1.160p.], O'.Sultanov[6.1.269p.], Sh.Makhmudov [7.1. 166p.], Kh. Borieva [8.1.212p.], B. Babadjanov [9.1.743p.], Z. Khatamova [10.1.212-214] can be listed.

Asomiddin Orinboev is mentioned as a scientist who studied sources related to the history of the Kokan Khanate in the research of Sh. «A. Orinboev recognized in his time that «Khulosat ul-akhval» is a very important source for studying the history of the khanate,» notes Sh. Vahidov [4.2.].

Z. Ilhomov touched upon the scientific researches of Asomiddin Orinboev during the analysis of the period of occupation of the Kokan Khanate by the Russian kingdom [5.2.].

O'Sultanov referred to the scientific legacy of Asomiddin Orinboev when he covered the history of the research of the work «History of Tashkent». It is noted that the life of the author, the history of the work, and the geographical names in it were revealed for the first time by Asomiddin Orinboev and O. Boriev.

Sh. Makhmudov referred to the research of Asomiddin Orinboev in the analysis of tax and taxation issues in the administrative management of the Kokan Khanate.

H. Borieva draws conclusions based on the scientific researches of Asomiddin Orinboev in the analysis of the history of the city of Tashkent and the origin of place names in the city. He emphasized the in-depth analysis of Muhammad Salihkhoja's information on the toponymy of the city of Tashkent. For example, the topography of Tashkent consisting of four branches and the geography of the surrounding areas included in the scope of these administrative units are presented in the interpretation of Asomiddin Orinboev and O. Boriev based on the work «History of Jadidayi Tashkent» . The table on the names of Tashkent gates in different sources was compiled by H. Borieva Asomiddin Orinboeva and O. Boriev based on the work entitled «Tashkent Muhammad Salih's classification» [8.2.].

B. Babadzhanov's research is unique in studying the history of the Kokan Khanate. Because the history of the khanate has been extensively researched. Asomiddin Orinboev's article «Neizvestnaya rukopis Kokandskogo khanstvo» and the study «Tashkent Muhammad Salih's classification» were usefully used in it.

In the researches of Z. Khatamova, it is noted that Asomiddin Orinboev left a scientific legacy that provides information about the economic life of the Kokan Khanate. In the in-depth study of the Khanate tax system, it was noted that the tax information presented in the work

«Khulasat ul-akhvol» by Asomiddin Orinboev was of great importance, and it was used in the comparative analysis of the data of Russian historians[10.2.].

The third group of the level of study of the research is made up of literature published in foreign countries, including J. Tulibaeva and G. Isakhan [11.1.], S. Elshibaev [12.1.], J. It is possible to include the researches of foreign scientists such as Abdukarimov [13.1.].

J. Tulibaeva and G. Volumes VII, IX, XI of the collection of Eastern manuscripts prepared by Asomiddin Orinboev and L.M. Epifanova were widely used in Isakhan's research. J. Tulibaeva and G. Isakhans considered these catalogs precisely from the point of view of covering the history of Kyrgyzstan in the sources related to the history of the Kokan Khanate.

In his research, Elshibaev emphasized that the research conducted by Asomuddin Orinboev on the work «Khulosat ul-akhval» is of special importance in the study of the history of Central Asia and Kazakhstan. Elshibaev included this article of Asomiddin Orinboev in the analysis of the researches of the Soviet period and on the eve of independence.

J. Abdukarimov noted that valuable information about the history of Tashkent in the 17th-19th centuries was included in the pamphlets of Asomiddin Orinboev and O. Boriev entitled «Tosh kent Muhammad Salih Tasnifida».

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the above three groups of literature shows that in the study of the history of the Kokand Khanate, the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Orinboev is still being referred to. Therefore, this situation serves as the main factor that indicates the necessity of the ongoing research.

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